

Universe Packets – 8 Theory

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June 17, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the two main equations of the 8 theory, the Lagrangian operator on the Lorentz manifold, and the coupling constants series, it is possible to claim that wrapping universe obey the same rules. In particular, given a key axiom we can state that all universes have the same interactions, i.e. strong weak and so on. the difference is than the stage of each manifold from the moment of singularity. Some manifolds are colder and older than others are, some are younger, and the distribution of masses and fermions clusters is of course different in each manifold.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ...$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.13)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s(n)} = 0 \quad (1.14)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M(1)} \frac{\partial M(1)}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s(n)} \frac{\partial s(n)}{\partial M(n)} \frac{\partial M(n)}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.15)$$

Equations describe the coupling constants series, which is built upon the notion of prime amount of curvature on the connected Lorentz manifold, which has the signature and invoked stationary. The stationary manifold is described by equation (2). Recall that according to the 8T the real reason of the acceleration is due wrapping universes that are topologically invariant, interacting at areas of maximal curvature causing the matrix to accelerate outward in an invariant rate. The subject of this paper is the following question: which laws does the wrapping universes/manifolds obey. the answer is binary, either the same laws as our manifold, or a different set of laws. Assuming nature is Lagrangian oriented the probable answer is that there is one set rule for all, generating a new set of rules to each universe is very unreasonable. In previous paper we built the axioms which needed so the same set of rules would apply to all.

Axiom (1): All universes are Lorentz manifolds

Axiom (2): All universes are stationary Lorentz manifold.

Axiom (3): Bosonic fields are isomorphic to primes or one.

Therefore, the same set of rules would apply if each universe has the infinite ring of the primes, located on $1/2$. And each universe are stationary, arbitrary variations vanish into matter, which means the group find by Gall Mann and also derived in the 8T, i.e. two quarks creating threefold combinations are universal for all manifolds. The reason they are universal is that they are ensuring stationarity of the manifold. The difference between each manifold than is the individual stage in which the manifold is at. Such a construction is shading light upon many questions left answered. First question, why 13.7B years? The answer is that it is just a random number; each manifold is flattened by other packets of manifolds at different time. Imagine the pressure a packet of universes implies on a dense and compressed manifold, such a picture than makes it reasonable for the inflation at singularity, and to why there was an inflation to begin with. Moreover such a construction also indicate that a manifold can not infinite number of dimensions as it is confined by many others. Such a confinement also makes each manifold flat.

In order for all universe to have the same interactions given by the coupling constants series and prime numbers, we are required to another axiom below axiom (3):

Axiom (3.1): The Prime Ring is isomorphic to itself in each manifold

I.e. the same primes appear at the same order in each manifold; else, each would have a different sequence of forces, weak after electric as an example. There is no reason to assume the axiom will not be satisfied, as one believes the primes sequence is invariant to all manifolds.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)